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Social Intelligence As Correlate Of Academic Engagement Among Public Secondary School Students In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined social intelligence as correlate of academic engagement among public secondary school students in Anambra State. Two specific purposes, two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of the study was 334 (male and female) secondary school students from the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling procedure was employed to determine the sample of the study. The instruments for data collection were two instruments: Tromso Social Intelligence Scale (TSIS) and Hart et al., (2011) Student Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). Since the instruments were standardized and extensively used, they were not subjected to re-validation and reliability. Pearson Product Moment Correlational analysis was used to analyze the data for the study. The findings of the study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Also, there is a high positive relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The researcher concluded based on the findings of the study that social intelligence has significant relationship with students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on these findings, it was recommended that administrators of public secondary schools should collaborate with curriculum planners to integrate subjects and academic activities that promote social intelligence among students.

Keywords: Academic Engagement, Gender, Social Intelligence, Students, Secondary School

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education in Nigeria builds on the competencies achieved during primary school. Secondary education in Nigeria builds upon the foundation laid during primary education and prepares students for higher academic pursuits or entry into the workforce. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her National Policy on Education asserted that the fundamental goals of secondary education are to prepare students for future academic pursuits and practical involvement in society. The realisation of the goals of secondary education is dependent on how properly students are engaged otherwise known as Academic Engagement.

The term academic engagement is commonly used to describe the level of involvement and investment that students have in their school experience (Abid & Akhtar, 2020). Ohamobi and Ezeaku (2015) defined students' academic engagement as a popular phrase used to characterize a student's relationship with the school. It is one of the concepts and variables used to assess the interactions between students and schools. Other terms relating to student academic engagement include school connection, school bonding, school atmosphere, school involvement and school engagement. Academic engagement encompasses both the psychological and behavioural aspects of students' connection to the school. Psychologically, academic engagement refers to students' sense of identification and appreciation for the outcomes of their schooling. The concept of academic engagement recognizes that students' success and well-being go beyond academic achievement alone. It acknowledges the importance of creating an inclusive and supportive school environment that fosters students' sense of belonging and encourages their active participation in various aspects of school life (McFarland et al., 2018). Academic engagement in the context of this study is defined as students' involvement and commitment to learning activities especially as it pertains to teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Sadly, the level of academic engagement in some secondary schools in Anambra State appears to be poor. According to Anierobi et al., (2022 p. 15), "public secondary schools have found it very difficult to optimally engage students in academic and non-academic activities" The researcher is worried that if this situation is left unchecked, it will have a negative effect of the quality of human capital in the state. It is therefore necessary to determine the factors that could contribute to poor student engagement. This situation can be attributed to factors like social intelligence.

Social intelligence is the ability to effectively interact with others, gaining the title of "people persons" (Baggiyam & Pankajam, 2017). Goleman (as cited in Obilor and Ikpa, 2019) defined social intelligence as the capacity for interpersonal effectiveness, leading to successful relationships with others. This means that social intelligence can be seen as an individual's capability to interact smoothly and successfully with others both verbally and non-verbally. Therefore, social intelligence involves the possession of social skills that foster positive relationships devoid of deviant behavioural patterns. Individuals with such skills can engage comfortably in verbal and non-verbal communications, thus facilitating and maintaining harmonious relationships in any setting. Schaap and Dippenaar (2017) saw social intelligence as the ability to establish and sustain positive relationships in various environments. Additionally, Odofoin (2022) stated that socially intelligent individuals tended to display assertiveness, with their level of social intelligence influencing their awareness, information management, connectedness, and interpersonal skills, ultimately impacting their success in academic and professional settings.

This suggests that social intelligence entails cultivating positive relationships with oneself and others, with self-awareness and understanding of others, thus enhancing effective interpersonal connections. Joseph and Lakshmi (as cited in Iviemu, 2021) noted that social intelligence was more descriptive of human beings than abstract intelligence. Social intelligence encompassed self-awareness, social consciousness, evolved social perceptions and opinions, and the readiness to manage societal change. Social intelligence involved optimally understanding one's environment and responding appropriately. Gkonou and Merce (2017) emphasised interpersonal awareness and social adeptness, including effective social relationship management, cooperation, collaboration, and group participation. Social intelligence is defined in the context of this study as a multidimensional construct that accurately measures an individual's ability to interpret others' intentions and motivations, negotiate complex social relationships, and navigate social environments. Social intelligence involves understanding one's own social responsibilities and relationships, as well as those of others. It has been established that nurturing students' social intelligence is crucial in fostering academic success, as it can enhance academic effort and persistence.

Gender has been reported to be a critical factor when analyzing social intelligence. Gender refers to the roles associated with being male or female. Gender is commonly used to explain how society assigns certain responsibilities to males and girls. Gender refers to the behaviours associated with masculinity and

femininity, as well as how people see their roles as male or female (Kauffman in Igbo et al., 2015). As a result, gender is linked to how people view themselves, with the majority of persons of the same sex identifying with specific characteristics. These characteristics influence children as they grow. Undoubtedly, the environment of a child influences his development (Igbo et al., 2015). Berk (as cited in Igbo et al., 2015) asserted that girls and boys were treated differently from birth. Girls are clothed in pink, and parents are kind with the girl child. However, these findings have not been empirically proven to be the case among public secondary school students in Anambra State. Therefore, this study explored social intelligence as correlate of students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The declining academic engagement of secondary school students in Anambra State has become a major concern for teachers, administrators, and parents. Observations from the researcher, as a teacher in a public secondary school, indicate a noticeable decline in student participation in academic activities. This disengagement is evident in students' lack of interest during lessons, minimal class participation, and reluctance to ask questions, all of which hinder learning. Additionally, many students fail to complete homework or submit substandard work, reflecting low motivation and a lack of responsibility for academic success.

Absenteeism further exacerbates the issue, leading to learning gaps and poor performance, which negatively affect both individual students and the overall school environment. While factors such as innate ability, home environment, and socio-economic status influence academic engagement, psychological factors like social intelligence play a critical role.

Existing studies have explored these issues, but research remains limited within the specific education zones under investigation. This study aims to examine the correlation between social intelligence and academic engagement among public secondary school students in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine social intelligence as correlate of students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Examine the relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female secondary school students in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement among public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement of male and female students among public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design. The area of this study was Anambra State. Anambra State is a state located in South Eastern Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 21,272 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population comprised of 9550 male students and 11,722 female students in 267 public secondary schools in Anambra

State according to Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC, 2024). The sample of the study was 400 (200 male and 200 female) senior secondary school two (SSII) students from the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A multistage sampling procedure was employed to determine the sample of the study. In the first stage, simple random sampling was used to select two education zones, Ogidi zone and Onitsha zone. In the second stage, stratified random sampling was used to draw five public secondary schools from each education zone (Ogidi and Onitsha), making a total of 10 schools. Using cluster sampling procedure in the third stage, the first stratum of SS2 students in the 10 selected public secondary schools were participants in the study. Each stratum of SS2 class has 40 students, and the 10 classes yielded a total of 400 students representing 20% of the entire SS2 students of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The instruments for data collection were two instruments: Tromso Social Intelligence Scale (TSIS) and Hart et al. (2011) Student Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ). Tromso Social Intelligence Scale (TSIS) contains 21 items measuring students' social intelligence. Student Engagement in the Schools Questionnaire (SESQ) contains 28 items. Both Scales were structured on a 4- point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Tromso Social Intelligence Scale (TSIS) and Hart et al., (2011) Student Academic Engagement in the Schools Questionnaires are used for the study. Since the instruments were standardized and extensively used, they were not subjected to re-validation and reliability test. The researcher briefed three research assistants on how to administer the instruments to the respondents and intimate them on the purpose of the study and how to exhibit good human relationship during data collection. There was a follow up visit in order to retrieve these questionnaires from the respondents who were not disposed to complete theirs immediately. Out of 400 copies of the instruments administered to the respondents, 334 copies were correctly completed and returned in good condition. The 334 copies of instrument returned represented 83.5% return rate. The 66 copies of the instrument not well completed or lost represented 16.5% questionnaire. The 334 copies of the instrument returned were considered adequate and used for the analysis of data. The research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlational to determine the relationship between the variables. Hypotheses 1-4 were tested using Pearson 'r' at 0.05 level of significance. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 26 was used for the data analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Pearson's Correlation between Social Intelligence and Students' Academic Engagement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Social Intelligence Academic Engagement	334	0.78	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson's correlation (r) presented in Table 1 shows that the correlation between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State was 0.78. This value indicates a high positive correlation. This suggests that as students' social intelligence increases, their academic engagement also increases and at a high rate.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation between Social Intelligence and Students Academic Engagement among Male and Female in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Male			
Social Intelligence	164	0.69	High positive relationship
Academic Engagement			
Female			
Social Intelligence	170	0.85	Very high positive relationship
Academic Engagement			

Table 2 presents the result of the Pearson’s correlation between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students. The Pearson’s correlation (r) obtained for the male sample was 0.69, which indicates a high positive relationship. For females, the r was 0.85. This value shows a very high positive relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among female students. When compared to the value obtained for the male students, the relationship between the two variables was stronger among the female students.

Hypothesis One: There will be no significant relationship between social intelligence and students’ Academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 6: Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Social Intelligence and Students’ Academic Engagement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remark
Social Intelligence	334	0.78	0.00	Significant
Students’ Academic Engagement				

The results in Table 6 show that there was a significant positive relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State, $r = 0.78$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between social intelligence and students academic engagement.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4

Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Social Intelligence and Students Academic Engagement in Males and Females in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remarks
Male:				
Social Intelligence Academic Engagement	164	0.69	0.000	Significant
Female:				
Social Intelligence Academic Engagement	170	0.85	0.000	Significant

As shown in Table 4, there was a significant positive relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State, $r = 0.69$, $p < 0.05$ (for males) and it was $r = 0.85$, $p < 0.05$ (for female). Since the p -values for both groups were less than 0.05, the null hypothesis stating that there was no significant relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement of male and female public secondary school students in Anambra State was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed a high positive relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two factors could account for the finding. First, students with higher social intelligence tend to exhibit better interpersonal skills, enabling them to build positive relationships with peers and teachers, which fosters a supportive learning environment. Second, socially intelligent students are more adept at managing their emotions and resolving conflicts, leading to increased classroom participation and motivation to learn. This finding is in agreement with that of Damina and General (2023) who noted that social intelligence enhances students' ability to interact effectively with their peers and teachers, creating a more engaging learning atmosphere. Similarly, Barragan et al., (2021) found that students with high social intelligence demonstrate greater self-regulation and motivation, which significantly enhance their academic engagement. Additionally, Mysore and Vijayalaxm (2020) documented that students who possess strong social intelligence skills show higher levels of classroom involvement and academic persistence.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between social intelligence and students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This result corroborates with Maquirea et al., (2017) who established that social intelligence plays a crucial role in students' adaptability and engagement in learning activities. In the same vein, Barragan et al. (2021) stated that students with higher levels of emotional and social intelligence perform better academically due to their ability to navigate social interactions effectively.

The findings of this study revealed a high positive relationship between social intelligence and academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding indicates that social intelligence could influence students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State irrespective of gender. This finding is consistent with the findings of Mysore and Vijayalaxmi (2020) who reported that social intelligence was positively related to academic engagement among adolescents. They documented that adolescents with high social intelligence demonstrated greater levels of academic engagement, supporting the present study's assertion that social intelligence is a key determinant of students' involvement in academic activities. Furthermore, Baños et al., (2023) found that emotional clarity and emotional repair positively influenced academic self-efficacy, which in turn enhanced both behavioural and emotional engagement. These findings suggest that emotional intelligence components contribute to academic engagement across gender, though their impact may manifest differently in male and female students.

Additionally, the findings of this study revealed a significant relationship between social intelligence academic engagement among male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of this study align with Baños et al., (2023) who reported that social intelligence had a high relationship with students' academic engagement. Baños et al., (2023) suggested that students with better emotional regulation and self-perception demonstrated that higher academic engagement.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concluded based on the findings of the study that social intelligence has significant relationship with students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of the study showed that social intelligence has a high positive relationship with students' academic engagement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Similarly, the findings of the study

showed that social intelligence have a high positive relationship with academic engagement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher proffered the following recommendations:

1. Administrators of public secondary schools should collaborate with curriculum planners to integrate subjects and academic activities that promote social intelligence among students. This can include group-based learning, conflict resolution training, and activities that enhance communication and interpersonal skills.
2. Principals of public secondary schools should design interventions that cater to the social learning needs of all students, ensuring equal opportunities for participation in leadership, teamwork and collaborative projects.

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